

PROBABILISTIC CHARACTERISTICS OF TWO-NODE COMMUNICATION NETWORKS IN REAL TIME

Shamsiyev R.N.

Alfraganus University, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

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Abstract. The problem of finding probabilistic characteristics of the states of a communication network with failures is considered. The network starts working from the zero state. Poisson flows of messages arrive at the nodes. The length of the messages is exponentially distributed random variables. If at the moment of receipt of a message at a node, this node is occupied by another message, then it leaves the network. A system of differential equations describing the operation of the network is compiled. Then, using the methods of operational calculus, this system of differential equations is solved.

Keywords: communication networks, probability, state, message flows, random variable, moment of occurrence.

Finding probabilistic characteristics of network states in real time is difficult due to the lack of a general mathematical apparatus for such problems. Only in special cases and under special conditions is this problem solved [1].

Let us consider a communication network of two nodes. Poisson flows of messages with parameter λ arrive at nodes 1 and 2. The length of the messages is exponentially distributed random variables, also with parameter λ .

Now let us give a visual description of the network operation. If node 1 is free at the moment a message is generated, it is transmitted to node 2 during the message length. If node 2 is busy with another message at the moment the message is sent, it is removed from the network (network failure), but if node 2 is free, it is removed from the network with probability $1/2$ and is transmitted to node 1 with probability $1/2$, after which it is removed from the network. If node 1 is busy with another message at the moment the message is generated, it is removed from the network (network failure). Messages generated in node 2 "behave" in exactly the same way as messages from node 1.

Let $P(t, n, m)$ denote the probability that at time t there are n messages in node 1 and m messages in node 2, where $n, m = 0, 1$. Then the following relation holds:

$$P(t, 0, 0) + P(t, 0, 1) + P(t, 1, 0) + P(t, 1, 1) = 1 \quad (1)$$

If we assume that the process starts from the zero state of the network, then the following relation is satisfied:

$$P(0, 0, 0) = 1, P(0, 0, 1) = P(0, 1, 0) = P(0, 1, 1) = 0 \quad (2)$$

which we will call the initial conditions.

The operation of the network is described at the mathematical level by the following equations:

$$P(t + \Delta t, 0, 0) = P(t, 0, 0)(1 - 2\lambda \cdot \Delta t) + P(t, 0, 1) \cdot \lambda \cdot \Delta t \cdot \frac{1}{2} + P(t, 1, 0) \cdot \lambda \cdot \Delta t \cdot \frac{1}{2} \quad (3)$$

The left side of this equation is the probability that at time $t + \Delta t$ there are no messages at nodes 1 and 2. According to the law of multiplication of probabilities of two independent events, the value $P(t + \Delta t, 0, 0)$ is equal to the probability of no messages at nodes 1 and 2 at time t ,

multiplied by the probability of no arrivals at both network nodes; plus the probability of there being one message at node 2 and no messages at node 1 at time t , multiplied by the probability that during time Δt one message from node 2 will be transmitted to node 1 and will leave the network with probability $1/2$; plus the probability of there being one message at node 1 and no messages at node 2 at time t , multiplied by the probability that during time Δt one message from node 1 will be transmitted to node 2 and will leave the network with probability $1/2$.

After moving $P(t, 0,0)$ to the left and dividing both sides by Δt , we obtain the equation:

$$\frac{P(t + \Delta t, 0,0) - P(t, 0,0)}{\Delta t} = -2\lambda P(t, 0,0) + (P(t, 0,1) + P(t, 1,0)) \cdot \lambda \cdot \frac{1}{2}$$

Here, by letting Δt tend to zero, we obtain the differential equation:

$$P'(t, 0,0) = -2\lambda P(t, 0,0) + (P(t, 0,1) + P(t, 1,0)) \cdot \lambda \cdot \frac{1}{2} \quad (4)$$

For another probability we have

$$P(t + \Delta t, 0,1) = P(t, 0,1)(1 - 2\lambda \cdot \Delta t) + P(t, 0,0) \cdot \lambda \cdot \Delta t + P(t, 1,1) \cdot \lambda \cdot \Delta t + P(t, 1,0) \cdot \lambda \cdot \Delta t \cdot \frac{1}{2}$$

From this equation it follows that the probability of finding one message in node 2 and no messages in node 1 at time $t + \Delta t$ is equal to the probability of finding one message in node 2 and no messages in node 1 at time t , multiplied by the probability that a message will not arrive at node 1, and a message from node 2 has not had time to be transmitted to its addressee; plus the probability of the absence of messages in nodes 1 and 2 at time t , multiplied by the probability that during time Δt one message arrived at node 2; plus the probability of finding one message in nodes 1 and 2, multiplied by the probability that during time Δt one message from node 1 will have time to be transmitted to node 2 and leave the network; plus the probability of finding one message in node 1 and no messages in node 2 at time t , multiplied by the probability that during time Δt one message from node 1 will be transmitted to node 2 and with probability $1/2$ will take the transmission place in node 2.

Here we also move $P(t, 0,1)$ to the left and divide by Δt , and then, by tending Δt to zero, we obtain the differential equation:

$$P'(t, 0,1) = -2\lambda P(t, 0,1) + (P(t, 0,0) + P(t, 1,1)) \cdot \lambda + P(t, 1,0) \cdot \lambda \cdot \frac{1}{2} \quad (5)$$

Applying the same probabilistic reasoning to the probabilities $P(t, 1,0)$ and $P(t, 1,1)$, we obtain the corresponding equations:

$$P'(t, 1,0) = -2\lambda P(t, 1,0) + (P(t, 0,0) + P(t, 1,1)) \cdot \lambda + P(t, 0,1) \cdot \lambda \cdot \frac{1}{2} \quad (6)$$

$$P'(t, 1,1) = -2\lambda P(t, 1,1) + (P(t, 0,1) + P(t, 1,0)) \cdot \lambda \quad (7)$$

By virtue of (1) we have

$$P'(t, 0,0) + P'(t, 0,1) + P'(t, 1,0) + P'(t, 1,1) = 0$$

Let's check that this equality is fulfilled by substituting (4)-(7) here:

$$\begin{aligned} & -2\lambda P(t, 0,0) + (P(t, 0,1) + P(t, 1,0)) \cdot \lambda \cdot \frac{1}{2} - \\ & -2\lambda P(t, 0,1) + (P(t, 0,0) + P(t, 1,1)) \cdot \lambda + P(t, 1,0) \cdot \lambda \cdot \frac{1}{2} - \\ & -2\lambda P(t, 1,0) + (P(t, 0,0) + P(t, 1,1)) \cdot \lambda + P(t, 0,1) \cdot \lambda \cdot \frac{1}{2} - \\ & -2\lambda P(t, 1,1) + (P(t, 0,1) + P(t, 1,0)) \cdot \lambda \equiv 0 \end{aligned}$$

i.e. relation (1) is satisfied for the solution of system (4)-(7). Then the probability $P(t, 1, 1)$ can be defined as

$$P(t, 1, 1) = 1 - P(t, 0, 0) - P(t, 0, 1) - P(t, 1, 0) \quad (8)$$

We will solve the system of differential equations (4)-(7) with initial conditions (2) using the operational calculus method. We will find the L -images of probabilities $P(t, 0, 0)$, $P(t, 0, 1)$, $P(t, 1, 0)$ and $P(t, 1, 1)$. We will denote these L -images by $F_0(z)$, $F_1(z)$, $F_2(z)$ and $F_3(z)$, respectively, i.e. $P(t, 0, 0) \xrightarrow{L} F_0(z)$, $P(t, 0, 1) \xrightarrow{L} F_1(z)$, $P(t, 1, 0) \xrightarrow{L} F_2(z)$, $P(t, 1, 1) \xrightarrow{L} F_3(z)$.

Then the derivatives have the following L -images:

$$P'(t, 0, 0) \xrightarrow{L} zF_0(z) - P(0, 0, 0) \text{ or by (1) we have } P'(t, 0, 0) \xrightarrow{L} zF_0(z) - 1;$$

$$P'(t, 0, 1) \xrightarrow{L} zF_1(z) - P(0, 0, 1) \text{ or } P'(t, 0, 1) \xrightarrow{L} zF_1(z);$$

$$P'(t, 1, 0) \xrightarrow{L} zF_2(z) - P(0, 1, 0) \text{ or } P'(t, 1, 0) \xrightarrow{L} zF_2(z);$$

$$P'(t, 1, 1) \xrightarrow{L} zF_3(z) - P(0, 1, 1) \text{ or } P'(t, 1, 1) \xrightarrow{L} zF_3(z);$$

Substituting the L -images of the desired probabilities and their derivatives into (4)-(7), we obtain a system of auxiliary equations of these differential equations:

$$\begin{cases} zF_0(z) - 1 = -2\lambda F_0(z) + \frac{1}{2}\lambda(F_1(z) + F_2(z)), \\ zF_1(z) = -2\lambda F_1(z) + \lambda(F_0(z) + F_3(z)) + \frac{1}{2}\lambda F_2(z), \\ zF_2(z) = -2\lambda F_2(z) + \lambda(F_0(z) + F_3(z)) + \frac{1}{2}\lambda F_1(z), \\ zF_3(z) = -2\lambda F_3(z) + \lambda(F_1(z) + F_2(z)), \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Subtracting the third equation of system (9) from the second equation, we obtain the equality:

$$z(F_1(z) - F_2(z)) = -2\lambda(F_1(z) - F_2(z)) - \frac{1}{2}(F_1(z) - F_2(z))$$

or else

$$\left(z + \frac{3}{2}\lambda\right)(F_1(z) - F_2(z)) = 0$$

Since $z + \frac{3}{2}\lambda \neq 0$, then from the last equality we have $F_1(z) \equiv F_2(z)$. Due to this identity and after transformations, system (9) has the form:

$$\begin{cases} (z + 2\lambda)F_0(z) = 1 + \lambda F_1(z), \\ \left(z + \frac{3\lambda}{2}\right)F_1(z) = \lambda(F_0(z) + F_3(z)), \\ (z + 2\lambda)F_3(z) = 2\lambda F_1(z), \end{cases}$$

or

$$\begin{cases} F_0(z) = \frac{1}{z+2\lambda} + \frac{\lambda}{z+2\lambda}F_1(z), \\ \left(z + \frac{3\lambda}{2}\right)F_1(z) = \lambda(F_0(z) + F_3(z)), \\ F_3(z) = \frac{2\lambda}{z+2\lambda}F_1(z) \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Substituting the expressions for $F_0(z)$ and $F_3(z)$ into the second equation of system (10), we obtain the equation for $F_1(z)$:

$$\left(z + \frac{3\lambda}{2}\right)F_1(z) = \frac{\lambda}{z + 2\lambda} + \frac{3\lambda^2}{z + 2\lambda}F_1(z).$$

After transformations we get:

$$\left(z + 2\lambda - \frac{1}{2}\lambda - \frac{3\lambda^2}{z + 2\lambda}\right)F_1(z) = \frac{\lambda}{z + 2\lambda}.$$

we multiply both parts of the equality by $2(z + 2\lambda)$:

$$(2(z + 2\lambda)^2 - \lambda(z + 2\lambda) - 6\lambda^2)F_1(z) = 2\lambda.$$

Where

$$F_1(z) = \frac{2\lambda}{z(2z + 7\lambda)}.$$

Expanding the fraction on the right into elementary parts, we obtain

$$F_1(z) = \frac{2}{7} \cdot \frac{1}{z} - \frac{2}{7} \cdot \frac{1}{z + \frac{7}{2}\lambda}.$$

Using the L –table [2] we find

$$F_1(z) \stackrel{L}{\leftarrow} P(t, 0, 1) = \frac{2}{7} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{7}{2}\lambda t}\right). \quad (11)$$

Since $F_1(z) \equiv F_2(z)$ then

$$F_2(z) \stackrel{L}{\leftarrow} P(t, 1, 0) = \frac{2}{7} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{7}{2}\lambda t}\right). \quad (12)$$

Substituting the expression for $F_1(z)$ into the first equation of system (10), we obtain

$$F_0(z) = \frac{1}{z + 2\lambda} + \frac{\lambda}{z + 2\lambda} \cdot \frac{2\lambda}{z(2z + 7\lambda)}.$$

Let's break down the expression on the right into elementary fractions:

$$F_0(z) = \frac{1}{7} \cdot \frac{1}{z} + \frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{1}{z + 2\lambda} + \frac{4}{21} \cdot \frac{\lambda}{z + \frac{7}{2}\lambda}.$$

Using the L –table we find

$$F_0(z) \stackrel{L}{\leftarrow} P(t, 0, 0) = \frac{1}{7} + \frac{2}{3}e^{-2\lambda t} + \frac{4}{21}e^{-\frac{7}{2}\lambda t}. \quad (13)$$

We find the last probability $P(t, 1, 1)$ from (8):

$$\begin{aligned} P(t, 1, 1) &= 1 - P(t, 0, 0) - P(t, 0, 1) - P(t, 1, 0) = 1 - \frac{1}{7} - \frac{2}{3}e^{-2\lambda t} - \frac{4}{21}e^{-\frac{7}{2}\lambda t} - \\ & - \frac{2}{7} + \frac{2}{7}e^{-\frac{7}{2}\lambda t} - \frac{2}{7} + \frac{2}{7}e^{-\frac{7}{2}\lambda t} = \frac{2}{7} - \frac{2}{3}e^{-2\lambda t} + \frac{8}{21}e^{-\frac{7}{2}\lambda t}. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Thus, we have proved the theorem:

Theorem. The solutions of differential equations (4)-(7) describing the operation of the network with failures are expressed through functions (11)-(14).

Sometimes it is useful to have probabilistic characteristics of networks in a stationary mode, i.e. characteristics that do not depend on time.

If we pass to the limit in functions (11)-(14) at $t \rightarrow \infty$, we find the stationary distribution of the state of the network:

$$P(0, 0) = \frac{1}{7}, P(0, 1) = P(1, 0) = \frac{2}{7}, P(1, 1) = \frac{2}{7}.$$

Conclusion. Due to the equality of the intensity parameters of incoming Poisson flows and exponentially distributed message lengths, there is a stationary mode of network operation.

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